

Acknowledgement

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The Application of *p*-Amino-*o*,*o'*-dimethylazobenzene as Adsorption Indicator in Argentometry of Halides and Thiocyanate

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AS an extension of our earlier studies¹⁻³ investigations on the application of *p*-amino-*o*,*o'*-azobenzene in precipitometry of halides (Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻) and thiocyanate (SCN⁻) using silver nitrate, have been made. The results of these investigations are presented in this communication.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. or G.R., E. Merck grade. Stock solutions of halides, thiocyanate and silver nitrate were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised by usual

methods. 0.2% solution of the dye was used (2-4 drops) as the indicator. The detailed experimental procedure has been described in our earlier communication¹.

In the argentometry of halides and thiocyanate, *p*-amino-*o*,*o'*-azobenzene dye is found to exhibit a sharp colour change from pink to yellow in the pH range 2-4.5. The indicator responded equally well in the reverse titration (Ag⁺ vs halides) with a colour change from yellow to pink at the end point. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—TITRATIONS OF HALIDES AND THIOCYANATE USING *p*-AMINO-*o*,*o'*-DIMETHYL AZOBENZENE AS ADSORPTION INDICATOR WITH Ag⁺ IONS*

Vol. of halide solution taken = 10.00 ml	
Concn. of halide/pseudohalide <i>M</i>	Vol. (ml), Concn. (<i>M</i>) of AgNO ₃
0.1 KCl/KI	9.98-10.00, 0.1
0.1 KBr/KSCN	10.00-10.02, 0.1
0.01 KCl/KBr	10.00, 0.02
0.02 KSCN/KI	9.98-10.00, 0.02
0.01 KCl/KBr	9.98-10.02, 0.01
0.01 KI/KSCN	10.00-10.02, 0.01

* Titrations were conducted in presence of 2.0-4.0 ml 0.01 *M* HNO₃. The colour change yellow to pink was sharp and reversible. Coagulation of Ag-halide/thiocyanate occurred just at the end point.

TABLE 2—TITRATIONS OF Ag⁺ IONS USING *p*-AMINO-*o*,*o'*-DIMETHYL AZOBENZENE AS INDICATOR WITH HALIDE/THIOCYANATE IONS*

Vol. of AgNO ₃ taken = 10.00 ml	
Concn. of AgNO ₃ <i>M</i>	Vol. (ml), Concn. (<i>M</i>) halide/pseudohalide
0.1	9.98-10.00, 0.1 KCl/KSCN
0.1	10.00-10.02, 0.1 KBr/KI
0.02	10.00, 0.02 KCl/KSCN
0.02	10.00-10.02, 0.02 KBr/KI
0.01	9.98-10.00, 0.01 KCl/KBr
0.01	10.00-10.02, 0.01 KI/KSCN

* Titrations were performed in presence of 2.5-4.5 ml 0.01 *M* HNO₃. Coagulation of Ag-halide/thiocyanate occurred earlier and dye adsorbed on the coagulated particles, but at equivalence point desorption of the dye starts. Changes are sharp and reversible.

Determination of iodide in a mixture of chloride and iodide: The titration of iodide in a mixture of chloride and iodide was carried out using *p*-amino-*o*,*o'*-azobenzene. The mixtures containing varying concentration were taken. The solution was adjusted to pH 4 by adding requisite amount of 0.1 *M* HNO₃. Four drops of the dye solution were added to the solution which was titrated against standard solution of silver nitrate. At that pH only iodide was titrated and the results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF IODIDE IN A MIXTURE OF CHLORIDE AND IODIDE USING *p*-AMINO-*o*'-DIMETHYLAZOBENZENE AS INDICATOR*

Concn. of solution <i>M</i>	Vol. of KI+KCl ml	Vol. of AgNO ₃ ml
0.1	10.00+10.00	10.05
0.2	10.00+10.00	10.00-10.02
0.01	10.00+10.00	10.02-10.04
0.05	10.00+10.00	10.00-10.02
0.1	5.00+10.00	4.98-5.02
0.2	5.00+10.00	5.00-5.02
0.01	7.00+10.00	6.98-7.03

* Titrations were performed at pH 4 where only I⁻ ions are titrated. The colour change yellow to pink was sharp and reversible and coagulation of AgX occurred near the end point

Results and Discussion

During the titration of halides thiocyanate by AgNO₃ using *p*-amino-*o*'-dimethylazobenzene as indicator, the colour change from yellow to pink at the end point is accompanied by a fall in pH from 4.05 to 3.60, which is more prominent in the case of iodide. The pH fall may be attributed to the deprotonation of the dye forming negatively charged dye ion. In the beginning AgX formed initially, is present in the medium containing abundance of halide ions. As the titration of X⁻ ions continues more and more AgX is formed and near the end point the amount of X⁻ ions is considerably reduced. These (X⁻) are, however, adsorbed on the surface of AgX at active points having adsorbed Ag⁺, forming weak mixed AgX-dye complex imparting a pink colour to the surface⁹. The colour changes in the reverse titration can similarly be explained.

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Dimethyldithiocarbamido-hydrizine as an Extractive Spectrophotometric Reagent for Determination of Palladium(II) and Nickel(II) Individually and also from Their Binary Mixture

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THE utility of organic thio-ligands having nitrogen atoms in their molecules has been widely investigated by several workers¹⁻⁹. Mention may be made of a few such reagents like thioamides, thioanilides, aminothiols, thiodiazoles, mercaptotriazoles, thio-carbamides and its various derivatives, aminothio-carboxylic acids, ruheanic acid, phenylhydrazine, sulfonic acid, etc. But their behaviour for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium and nickel, suffer from narrow pH range of extraction, variable composition of the complexes with variation of pH, interference from commonly associated metal ions, and difficulty of analytical separation of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} from their binary mixture. All the above mentioned difficulties have been overcome in this present method of estimation of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II}. Moreover, the present reagent claims its superiority over the classical reagent, dimethylglyoxime for enabling the separation of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II}. The work involves the application of dimethyldithiocarbamido-hydrizine¹⁰ (METHALZIN), a newly introduced ligand, which can suitably be utilised for the spectrophotometric determination of Pd^{II} and Ni^{II} individually and also by separation from their binary mixture.

Methalzin forms a brown complex with Pd^{II} in aqueous solution within pH range 1.5-3.6, the complex being extractable in chloroform while the aqueous solution of Ni^{II} forms a brownish yellow complex with the reagent within pH range 7.5-9.6, the complex being equally soluble in chloroform. Thus by simply maintaining the proper pH of extraction, separation and determination of these two metal ions have been successfully achieved.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II}: The metal ion solutions were prepared by dissolving known weights of AnalaR nickel chloride and palladium chloride in double-distilled water. The solutions were standardised by usual methods¹¹ using dimethylglyoxime.

Reagent solution: Dimethyldithiocarbamido-hydrizine (METHALZIN) was prepared by the method¹² described earlier. As the excess amount of reagent has no adverse effect on absorbance. A 0.025% (w/v) solution of the reagent in absolute alcohol was used throughout the experiment. All other reagents and chemicals used were of AnalaR